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Household Availability of at Least One Computer and Internet Connection in Italian Regions

Increased by 96% Between 2005 and 2022

Istat calculates the household availability of at least one computer and an internet connection. The variable refers to the percentage of households with an internet connection and at least one personal computer (including desktop computers, laptops, notebooks, and tablets; excluding smartphones, PDAs with telephone functions, e-book readers, and gaming consoles). The data covers Italian regions from 2005 to 2022.

Trend of Household Availability of at Least One Computer and Internet Connection in Italian Regions in 2022. The analysis of household availability of at least one computer and an internet connection in Italian regions for the year 2022 shows a varied landscape, with significant geographical differences. Trentino-Alto Adige ranks at the top with 77.5% of households equipped with at least one computer and internet access, highlighting a notably high level of domestic digitalization. Close behind are regions like Veneto and Lombardy, with percentages of 73.3% and 72.9% respectively, confirming the trend towards good technological availability in Northern Italy. In the center, Lazio records a percentage of 71.7%, positioning itself just below the top three regions, followed by Friuli-Venezia Giulia and Marche, with very similar values. This reflects a fairly uniform technological adoption in central regions, despite some slight variations. When comparing regions, there is a decreasing gradient moving towards the South and the Islands, with Sicily, Puglia, Basilicata, and Calabria registering the lowest percentages, at 60.6%, 60.3%, 58.3%, and 56.9% respectively. This technological gap reflects a broader disparity in terms of infrastructure and digital investments, highlighting a North-South division that persists in the Italian landscape. Overall, these data indicate that the digital divide remains a relevant issue in Italy, with significant regional differences in access to digital technologies. This underscores the importance of targeted policies to promote universal access to the internet and computer technologies as a lever for economic and social development, especially in less equipped regions.

Trend Between 2005 and 2022. The analysis of data on the household availability of at least one computer and internet connection in Italian regions highlights significant digital progress between

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2005 and 2022. There is a broad growth in technological equipment at the domestic level in all regions, with percentage variations reflecting intense infrastructural development and increased accessibility to digital technologies. Sicily shows the most marked increase in percentage terms, with an incredible leap of 157.87%, rising from 23.5% to 60.6%. This indicates not only a significant improvement in access to computer technologies but also a substantial catch-up compared to other regions. Valle d'Aosta and Liguria also recorded notable increases, with percentage variations of 124.25% and 132.28% respectively, despite starting from relatively low bases in 2005. Interestingly, regions with already high technological availability in 2005, such as Lombardy and Trentino-Alto Adige, have maintained robust growth rates, although in percentage terms they are less spectacular compared to regions that started from a more backward position. Trentino-Alto Adige, for example, saw a growth of 100.26%, establishing itself as the region with the highest availability in 2022. The growth in Molise and Campania is also remarkable, with absolute increases exceeding 35 percentage points and percentage variations surpassing 120%. This highlights efforts in modernization and reducing the digital divide even in traditionally less advanced regions. Basilicata represents the case of the lowest percentage growth, with an increase of 65.63%, which, although significant, underscores how some areas may have encountered more difficulties in keeping pace with digital evolution. Overall, the data reflect a positive trend towards digitalization in Italy, with evident benefits in terms of access to information, educational opportunities, and work. However, the regional disparities in growth rates emphasize the importance of targeted policies to support less advanced regions, ensuring equitable access to digital technologies across the entire national territory.

Italian Macro-Regions Between 2005 and 2022. The analysis of data on household availability of at least one computer and internet connection in Italian macro-regions between 2005 and 2022 reveals a significant transformation in the country's technological landscape. In 2005, the percentage of households with at least one computer varied considerably from one region to another, with the North showing slightly higher values (36.7% for the North in general, with a subdivision of 36.2% for the North-West and 37.3% for the North-East) compared to the Center (38.6%) and decidedly higher compared to the Mezzogiorno, including the South (29.7%) and the Islands (26.6%). In 2022, there is a generalized increase in the availability of computers and internet access in all regions, with the North reaching an average of about 71%, the Center 70.4%, and the Mezzogiorno showing a notable increase, reaching up to 62.4% for the South and 62.3% for the Islands. The percentage variation demonstrates significant growth, especially in southern and insular regions: the Islands registered an increase of 134.21%, the South 110.44%, and the Mezzogiorno in general 117.42%, highlighting a reduction in the technological gap between the North and South of the country. The absolute variation shows substantial increases in all macro-regions, with the North-West marking the highest absolute increase (34.6%), while the Center presents the most contained increase (31.8%). These data reflect not only an improvement in access to computer technologies but also a change in the perception of the importance of internet connectivity as an essential tool for education, work, and daily life. In conclusion, the analysis of data from 2005 to 2022 highlights a marked evolution in Italy's technological infrastructure, with an acceleration in the adoption of computers and internet connections that contributes to overcoming historical regional disparities. This technological progress is crucial for the socio-economic development of the country, promoting digital inclusion and offering new opportunities in various areas of society.

North-South Divide. The analyzed data indicate the existence of a North-South divide in Italy in terms of household availability of at least one computer and internet access. However, the divide has significantly reduced between 2005 and 2022. In 2005, regions in Northern Italy had higher percentages of households with at least one computer and internet access compared to the Center and especially to the Mezzogiorno, including the South and the Islands. For example, the North generally had a computer availability percentage around 36.7%, while in the Mezzogiorno (South and Islands) the percentages were significantly lower, with the South at 29.7% and the Islands at 26.6%. In 2022, the availability of computers and internet access increased in all regions, but the increase was particularly marked in the Mezzogiorno. The Islands registered the highest percentage increase (134.21%), followed by the Mezzogiorno in general (117.42%) and the South (110.44%). These increases indicate a significant improvement in technological infrastructure and internet access in the South and the Islands, which has contributed to reducing the gap with the North. Despite this reduction, the gap is not completely closed. In 2022, the Northern regions still maintain a slightly higher percentage of computer availability and internet access compared to the Mezzogiorno. However, the distance between the two areas has markedly decreased compared to 2005, signaling progress towards greater digital equity in the country. This improvement is fundamental for Italy's socio-economic development, as greater digital inclusion allows wider access to education, remote work, digital public services, and economic growth opportunities, reducing regional disparities.

Conclusions. The value of household availability of a computer and internet connection grew by an average of 96.92% in all Italian regions. The data show a significant reduction in the North-South divide. Economic policies to improve household availability of at least one computer and internet connection in Italian macro-regions should be oriented towards an inclusive strategy. An effective approach could include financial incentives for families and businesses, investments in digital infrastructure, and educational programs to increase digital awareness and skills. First and foremost, it is crucial to increase investments in telecommunications infrastructure, especially in rural areas and regions of the Mezzogiorno, where the digital divide is more pronounced. This includes modernizing existing networks and promoting the spread of ultra-broadband and 5G, to ensure fast and reliable internet connection to all citizens. Additionally, local and national governments could introduce tax incentives for families purchasing technological devices or subscribing to internet contracts. This could include tax deductions or direct subsidies, particularly for low-income families, to make technology more accessible. Finally, it is important to promote educational and training programs aimed at improving the digital skills of all citizens, from the youngest to the oldest. Such investment in education will not only increase the demand for internet services but also make the population more capable of leveraging the opportunities offered by the digital economy. Last but not least, encouraging public-private partnerships for financing and implementing digital infrastructure projects can accelerate technological development and its adoption. Collaborations with technology companies could lead to initiatives aimed at improving accessibility and the use of computers and the internet, especially in schools and disadvantaged communities. These policies, along with a constant commitment to evaluate and adjust strategies based on evolving needs and technologies, can significantly contribute to reducing the digital divide in Italy, promoting more equitable access to digital resources, and supporting the socio-economic development of all regions.

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Appendix

Variazione Percentuale della Disponibilità di almeno un Computer e Connessione Internet (2005-2022)